

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RELATIONS BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE ORGANIZATION OF ISLAMIC COOPERATION

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ABSTRACT

This article examines Uzbekistan's relations with the Organization of Islamic Cooperation. The Organization of Islamic Cooperation is the second largest international organization after the United Nations, with 57 member states spread across four continents. The organization was established in response to the fire that broke out at the Al-Aqsa Mosque in occupied Jerusalem during the First Islamic Summit.

Introduction. The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) is an intergovernmental international organization established on September 25, 1969, at the first meeting of the heads of Islamic countries held in Rabat, Morocco.

It was founded and its charter was adopted in 1973 at the 3rd Conference of Foreign Ministers of Islamic Countries in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia.

Originally called the Organization of the Islamic Conference (OIC). This international organization received its current name, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), in 2011. The official working languages of the OIC are English, Arabic, and French.

Currently, the OIC unites a total of 55 states on the basis of religious unity, including the independent Central Asian states, as well as the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO). According to the OIC Charter, its goals are to promote Islamic solidarity among member states, strengthen cooperation in the economic, social, cultural, scientific and other fields, strive to eliminate racial discrimination and all forms of colonialism, determine measures to maintain peace and security, and support the struggle of the Palestinian Arab people to restore their rights and liberate their lands.

The governing bodies of the OIC are: the Conference of Heads of State and Government, the Conference of Foreign Ministers, and the Secretariat headed by the Secretary-General. The Conference of Heads of State and Government of the OIC has been convened every 3 years since 1981. The Conference of Foreign Ministers of the OIC is convened annually, and sometimes as necessary.

Theoretical foundations. The headquarters of the OIC are located in Jeddah. The Islamic Development Bank and the Standing Committee on Cooperation in Science and Technology operate under the OIC. Since 1975, the OIC has been granted observer status at the United Nations (UN). The Republic of Uzbekistan has been a full member of the OIC since 1996.

The main goals and objectives of the OIC are:

- to strengthen the bonds of friendship and solidarity between member states;
- to resolve problems that have arisen in the Islamic world;
- to respect the internal laws of states;
- to protect human rights;
- to promote the economic development of member states;
- to eliminate some unfair and misleading information about the Islamic religion;
- to organize scientific research with institutions in various fields in the countries.

Today, 57 countries with a population of nearly 2 billion are members of the OIC. This broad-based cooperation plays an important role in achieving the noble goals of preserving and developing the sacred values of Islam, strengthening solidarity among Muslim nations, ensuring sustainable development, and contributing to the development and well-being of the peoples of the organization's member countries.

The UN, Russia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and the Central African Republic have observer status in the OIC. Uzbekistan was admitted to the organization as an observer in October 1995, and as a full member on October 2, 1996. It should be noted that Uzbekistan acceded to the new Statute of the OIC on December 14, 2015. The Statute of the OIC was ratified by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan in April 2016.

The Uzbek side recognizes the OIC as an influential and effective forum of the countries of the Islamic world, which recognize our holy religion as a factor of peace and development. Therefore, we are interested in the strengthening of this Organization and the consistent development of our mutual relations.

Official delegations of our country regularly participate in the OIC summits and the annual sessions of the OIC Council of Foreign Ministers. In particular, in recent years, Uzbekistan's cooperation with the OIC has become more active and has reached a new stage of mutual relations.

In this regard, the 43rd session of the OIC Council of Foreign Ministers, held in Tashkent on October 18-19, 2016, was of particular importance. In his speech at the opening ceremony of this session, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev drew attention to the priority tasks of Uzbekistan during its chairmanship of the OIC Council of Foreign Ministers (from October 2016 to July 2017).

As the Head of our state noted, the fact that the theme "Education and Enlightenment – the Path to Peace and Creativity" has been set as the main idea of the agenda of the 43rd session has a deep symbolic meaning. This idea is in line with the famous hadith "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave." From this perspective, the initiatives put forward by the Uzbek side are directly related to the development of science and enlightenment.

The President of Uzbekistan also put practical proposals for the development of science, spirituality and enlightenment on the agenda in his speech at the first OIC Summit on Science and Technology held in Astana, Kazakhstan, on September 10, 2017. Currently, the noble initiatives announced by the head of our country from the high podiums of the OIC are being widely implemented.

As you know, on October 7-8, 2019, the 6th annual seminar of the OIC Independent Standing Commission on Human Rights on the topic "The Importance of Promoting and

Protecting Youth Rights in Building Peaceful, Democratic Societies and Sustainable Development” was held in our capital. The participants of the international conference supported the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to adopt the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth, put forward at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly.

It is no coincidence that the OIC Independent Standing Commission on Human Rights chose the issue of youth rights for its major international conference. After all, young people today constitute a large part of the population in most countries, especially in OIC member states. Our indifferent approach to this segment of the population inevitably threatens the stability and peace of our societies.

The participants of the Tashkent Conference adopted the final document - the Tashkent Declaration on Youth Rights in the Member States of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation. The Declaration outlines important future initiatives to be implemented at the international level and by the OIC Member States to fully ensure the rights of youth.

Today, cooperation between Uzbekistan and the OIC is developing steadily. In particular, the close relations established between the National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the OIC Independent Standing Commission on Human Rights play a special role.

On May 4-5, 2024, the Uzbek delegation led by the Speaker of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan N. Ismoilov participated in the 15th Summit of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation dedicated to the theme "Developing Solidarity and Cooperation for Sustainable Development".

The head of the Uzbek delegation spoke about the work being carried out in Uzbekistan within the framework of the OIC, which makes a worthy contribution to the unity and development of the Islamic world. He also reported on the fact that, thanks to the political will of the leaders of the Central Asian states, an environment based on mutual trust and good neighborly relations has been formed in our region, as well as on the achievements made within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy. At the end of the summit, relevant OIC documents were adopted.

A meeting was also held with the President of the Republic of Gambia, Adama Barrow, within the framework of the summit. The President of the Gambia noted that the OIC is gaining influence because, unlike other international organizations, its members are united by the holy religion of Islam, Uzbekistan is a leading country in Central Asia, is developing rapidly today, and most importantly, is achieving results.

The Secretary General of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, Ibrahim Hussein Toha, noted during a meeting with the Uzbek delegation that he has a good impression of Uzbekistan and always remembers this country with warmth, and that Uzbekistan, which has a deep historical and cultural heritage, has been making a worthy contribution to ensuring the unity and solidarity of the Islamic world in the activities of the OIC.

In addition, within the framework of the event, dialogues and meetings were held with the heads of delegations of Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, Turkey, and Indonesia.

Conclusion. Today, new Uzbekistan is recognized as an active and reliable partner not only in the Central Asian region, but also in the world community. The large-scale reforms carried out in our country, the policy aimed at glorifying human dignity, and the strategy of sustainable development are gaining increasing attention in the international arena. During the years of independence, our state has chosen the path of openness and mutually beneficial cooperation in foreign policy, and has defined close cooperation with international organizations, in particular the United Nations, as a strategic direction.

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